

Data for Policy 2021

14 – 16 September 2021
Virtual

Welcome

It is a pleasure to welcome you to Data for Policy, the premier global forum for multiple disciplinary and cross-sector discussions around the theories, applications and implications of data science innovation in governance and the public sector.

Data for Policy 2021, our sixth conference, following the momentous events of 2020, has the theme ‘Lessons for policy-data interactions after Covid-19’. It is the right time to recognise the additional focus on data throughout the whole of society as a consequence of the Covid-19 pandemic, and the opportunities this creates for learning about and developing data and policy interactions. We know that the impact of the pandemic continues, and thus the committee and conference organisers necessarily took the decision to continue in virtual format for a further year.

The conference will open with a plenary panel chaired by Stefaan Verhulst (GovLab and NYU). The panellists Chinwe Ochu (Nigeria Centre for Disease Control), Brennan Lake (Cuebiq) and Chris Wiggins (Columbia University and New York Times) will discuss the impact of the pandemic and the importance of data in the response of their respective fields: public health, the private sector, academia and the media.

We have two excellent keynote speakers: Prof Karen Yeung is Interdisciplinary Professorial Fellow in Law, Ethics and Informatics at Birmingham Law School and the University of Birmingham School of Computer Science. She will speak on the topic of algorithmic governance. Dame Wendy Hall, Regius Professor of Computer Science, Associate Vice President (International Engagement) and Executive Director of the Web Science Institute, University of Southampton will speak on data stewardship. We also have an international panel for our opening plenary, discussing “Different Perspectives on the Impact of Covid-19 on Data Ecosystems”.

As ever, our individual and panel presentations will be broad-ranging and cross-disciplinary. The six thematic areas of interest of the standard tracks will ensure that content extends from the highly technical through to real-world applications. The three special tracks will showcase highly topical work on data-driven innovation for sustainability, mobility as a service, and tools to tackle misinformation.

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Data for Policy 2021

Lessons for Policy-Data Interactions after Covid-19

Conference Programme (September 14th – 16th)

DAY 1, 14th September, London time

15:00 – 15:05 **Opening Remarks**

Welcome to the Conference - Zeynep Engin, Founder of Data for Policy

Arrangements for the Conference - Emily Gardner, Data for Policy Community Manager

15:05 – 16:00 **Opening Plenary Panel**

“Different Perspectives on the Impact of Covid-19 on Data Ecosystems”

Chair: Stefaan **Verhulst**, GovLab

Covid-19 has brought upheaval in all sectors and parts of life. The coronavirus has transformed how we live, how we work and how organisations operate. It has been devastating for many. This session will focus on how Covid-19 has impacted “data and policy” from the perspectives of four three different actors of the data ecosystem.

Speakers:

Brennan **Lake**, Senior Director of Research Partnerships at Cuebiq

Chinwe **Ochu**, Director, Prevention, Programmes & Knowledge Management at the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control

Chris **Wiggins**, Professor at Columbia University and Chief Data Scientist at The New York Times

16:00 – 16:40 **Session 1**

Standard Track 1.A: *Data-driven Transformations in Policy and Governance*

Chair: Eric Meyer

[4] *“ACROSS: Towards user journeys for the delivery of cross-border services ensuring data sovereignty”* Francesco **Mureddu***

[60] *“Conceptualising and measuring data in global value chains”* Maria **Savona*** and Javier Lopez **Gonzalez**

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† indicates Q&A participant at the live conference

[69] *“Data Sharing for Common Purpose: Policy Frameworks and Implications post Covid-19”* Catherine **Mulligan***, Nadia **Hewett** and Kimberly **Bella**

[50] *“Cultivating New Platform Imaginaries to Connect Open Data and Social Justice”* Anjali **Mehta†**, Gulsen **Guler***, Amanda **Greene†** and Shreyasha **Paudel†**

16:40 – 16:50 **Short Break**

16:50 – 17:30 **Session 2**

Standard Track 2.A: Special Panel [45] - *Towards smart city planning – digital twins and parallel world scenarios to support better public policies?*

Organiser(s): Franziska **Sielker***, Timea **Nochta**, Li **Wan***, Claudia **Yamu***, Markus **Kraft**, Jethro **Akroyd**, Amit **Bhave***, Aurel **von Richthofen**, Pieter **Herthogs***, Gourab Karmakar, Aravind Devanand, Vsk Murthy **Balijpalli** and Gemma **Burgess**

Chair: Franziska Sielker

[45a] *“Digital twins and smart city planning – Examples from Cambridge”* Li **Wan*** and Timea **Nochta**

[45b] *“A knowledge-graph approach to cross-domain data integration – implications for planning”* Markus **Kraft**, Jethro **Akroyd** and Amit **Bhave***

[45c] *“Addressing Challenges of Urban Policy Making and City Planning with a Cities Knowledge Graph”* Aurel **von Richthofen**, Pieter **Herthogs*** and Markus **Kraft**

[45d] *“Digital twins and smart city planning - New options through knowledge graphs for managing liberalized energy markets in Singapore”* Franziska **Sielker***, Hou Yee **Quek**, Aravind **Devanand**, Gourab **Karmakar** and VSK Murthy **Balijepalli**

17:30 – 18:10 **Session 3**

Standard Track 6.A: *Data to Tackle Global Issues and Dynamic Societal Threats*

Chair: Jon Crowcroft

[76] *“Reporting and Registering Domestic Violence Against Women in Latin America: A Comparative Analysis between Mexico, Brazil, and Colombia”* Zinnya **del Villar***, Anna **Spinardi** and Ivette **Yáñez**

[86] *“New methods and novel data for estimating seasonal hunger”* Conor **Hennessy*** and Leigh **Anderson**

[89] *“Mapping 200 million European buildings in 2.5D to support policy-making”* Nikola **Milojevic-Dupont***, Marvin **Bensch**, Filip **Biljecki**, Niko **Heeren**, Jiawei **Hu**, Lynn H. **Kaack**, Steffen **Lohrey**, Peter-Paul **Pichler**, Felix **Wagner**, Aicha **Zekar**, Marius **Zumwald** and Felix **Creutzig**

[108] *“Sub-national trends in demography and women’s socio-economic development: A harmonized dataset covering 51 countries [1990-2019]”* Camille **Belmin***, Roman **Hoffmann**, Mahmoud **Elkasabi**, Peter-Paul **Pichler** and Helga **Weisz**

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† indicates Q&A participant at the live conference

[96] *“Leveraging household phone surveys to monitor mobility induced labor market consequences of the Covid-19 pandemic in Kenya”* Markus **Heemann***, Utz Johann **Pape** and Dennis **Egger**

18:10 – 18:40 Networking Break

18:40 – 19:20 Session 4

Standard Track 3.A: Policy Frameworks, Governance and Management of Data-driven Innovations

Chair: Eleonore Fournier-Tombs

[47] *“Providing Access to Justice Data for Legal/Tech Innovation in the UK”* Stergios **Aidinlis***, Hannah **Smith**, John **Armour** and Jeremias **Adams-Prassl**

[51] *“Covid-19: An exploration of consecutive systemic barriers to pathogen-related data sharing during a pandemic”* Yo **Yehudi***, Carole **Goble** and Caroline **Jay**

[78] *“How can interoperability stimulate the use of digital public services? An analysis of national interoperability frameworks and e-Government maturity in the EU”* Alexandra **Campmas***, Nadina **Iacob**[†] and Felice **Simonelli**

[116] *“Precision policies and Local Content targets in resource-rich developing countries: the case of the oil and gas sector in Mozambique”* Marika **Arena**, Giovanni **Azzone**, Laura **Dell'Agostino*** and Francesco **Scotti**

19:20 – 20:00 Session 5

Standard Track 4.A: Ethics, Equity and Trust in Policy Data Interactions

Chair: Laura Acion

[26] *“Empowering the research and statistical community in the application of data ethics”* Emma **Walker**, Simon **Whitworth** and Alice **Toms***

[34] *“Responsible Innovation for Digital Identity Systems”* Nishant **Anand*** and Irina **Brass**

[63] *“Data Ethics Skills: Professionalising Data Ethics in the Public Sector”* Natalia **Domagala***

[109] *“The OECD Good Practice Principles for Data Ethics in the Public Sector: Challenges to Effective Implementation”* Arturo **Rivera**, Omar **Bitar*** and Natalia **Domagala**

20:00 – 20:10 Short Break

20:10 – 20:50 Session 6

Standard Track 2.B: Data Technologies and Analytics for Policy and Governance

Chair: Innar Liiv

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† indicates Q&A participant at the live conference

[10] “Daily updated website analysis on the reaction of companies to the Coronavirus pandemic in Germany” Jan **Kinne*** and David **Lenz**

[79] “Local Data Spaces for Local Policy Research: Leveraging Trusted Research Environments for Granular, Secured, Local Policy Research in the Age of COVID-19” Jacob **Macdonald***, Maurizio **Gibin**, Mark **Green** and Simon **Leech**

[99] “Analysis of Preferential Utilisation Tariffs using machine learning” Ioannis **Kaloskampis***, Faisal **Samin**, Cailin **Murphy**, Silvia **Lui** and Thomas **Hannan**

[103] “Leveraging a National Big Data Source to Measure Cost and Affordability Gaps between Current and Healthy Diets: an analysis for Argentina during the Pandemic Year” Florencia **Camara***, Luciana **Castronuovo**, Victoria **Tiscornia**, Leila **Guarnieri** and Maria Elizabeth **Pizarro**

20:50

Day Close

Conference Programme (September 14th – 16th)

DAY 2, 15th September, London time

13:00 – 13:05 Day opening

13:05 – 13:40

Session 7

Special Track II.A: *Facilitating Data-Driven Innovation for Sustainability: Policy Frameworks and Measures for Data Governance*

Track Chair: Masaru **Yarime**

[12] “Technology to Sustainable Development Challenges and risks arising from the Internet of Value - Governance and privacy issues through distributed ledger technology” Danielle Mendes Thame **Denny***

[32] “Exploring the Partnerships Processes for Enabling the Use of Big Data in National Monitoring of the Sustainable Development Goals” Cameron **Allen***, Grant **Cameron** and Hayden **Dahmm**

[92] “Examining the Role of Satellite Data in Eradicating Polio in Nigeria: A Socioeconomic Analysis” Mariel **Borowitz***, Janet **Zhou**, Krystal **Azelton** and Isabelle-Yara **Nassar**

[55] “Using social media data analysis to assist vaccine safety monitoring of COVID-19 vaccines” Clement **Schlegel***, Xueping **Peng**, Tao **Shen**, Alvin **Wang**, Michael **Agnew**, Leah **Gerrard**, Warren **Arndt**, Guodong **Long** and Allison **Clarke**

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13:45 – 14:25 **Session 8**

Standard Track 2.C: Data Technologies and Analytics for Policy and Governance

Chair: Catherine Mulligan

[13] *“Artificial Intelligence and Big Data in Fraud Analytics: Identifying the Main Data Protection Challenges for Public Administrations”* Thomas **Tombal** and Anthony **Simonofski***

[59] *“Promoting Digital Inclusion through Usability Evaluation of Online Public Participation Platforms: A Case Study using Google Analytics and Google Tag Manager”* Annelieke **van den Berg***, Sarah **Giest** and Wessel **Kraaij**

[97] *“Facilitating Data Sharing and Ownership in a Future Insurance Market”* Zena **Wood*** and Phil **Godsiff**

[56] *“Dynamically Identifying Community-level COVID-19 Impact Risks”* William **Seitz***

14:25 – 14:35 **Short Break**

14:35 – 15:15 **Session 9**

Standard Track 5.A: Algorithmic Governance

Chair: Mustafa F. Ozbilgin

[57] *“Accounting for technological agency in smart energy systems governance: towards a conceptual basis”* Paula **Hansen*** and Tedd **Mose**

[43] *“An iterative regulatory process for robot governance: Building a dynamic framework for evidence utilization in policymaking for robot technologies”* Hadassah G. **Drukarch** †, Carlos **Calleja Ahmad** † and Eduard **Fosch Villaronga***

[58] *“Machine Learning for Mediation in Armed Conflicts”* Rob **Procter**, Miguel **Arana-Catania** and Felix **van Lier***

15:15 – 15:55 **Session 10**

Special Track III: Systemic engagement: Mobility as a Service (MaaS) and the design challenge of inclusion, sustainability, and data ownership

Track Chairs: Ronit **Purian** and Avram (**Avi**) **Cohen**

[39] *“Optimizing shared (autonomous) demand-responsive transport: A case study of Jerusalem”* Golan **Ben-Dor***, Ido **Klein**, Aleksey **Ogulenko**, Eran **Ben-Elia**, Issa **Zananiri**, Eitan **Bluer** and Itzhak **Benenson**

[67] *“Dynamic Conceptual Model for (Big) Data Management for Urban Planning in Self-Organizing Cities”* Jenni **Partanen***

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† indicates Q&A participant at the live conference

[74] *“Participatory Backcasting for Achieving Desired Co-produced Mobility Futures: A Case Study of MaaS in Greater Manchester”* Sigita **Zigure***, Mahmud **Tantoush**, Solon **Solomou**, May **Bassanino** and Ulysses **Sengupta**

[85] *“Do shared micromobility options reduce traffic congestion? Evidence from a natural experiment”* Camila Z. **Apablaza***, Savannah J. **Horner** and Omar Isaac **Asensio**

15:55 – 16:25 **Networking Break**

16:25 – 17:05 **Keynote Lecture 1**

“The production of ‘regulatory science’ through in-the-wild technology testing: Live facial recognition technology as the Thalidomide of AI?”

Professor Karen Yeung, Birmingham Law School

Chair: Leigh Anderson

Abstract: As governments everywhere embrace data-driven tools and systems, ‘in the wild’ testing of, and experimentation with, data-driven technologies within the public sector appears to be growing. Use of biometric technologies has grown rapidly in recent years, despite warnings of the dangers many applications pose to basic liberties and democratic freedoms. Focussing on in-the-wild ‘trials’ of live Facial Recognition Technologies (FRT), I reflect on the challenges that arise in identifying, nurturing and sustaining the boundaries of their acceptable use, including the need for prohibition, drawing from historical experience of earlier technology testing and insights from several disciplinary perspectives. While there is a potentially important and valuable role for live testing, there is an urgent need for clear, standardised protocols and meaningful oversight mechanisms to govern the design, conduct and evaluation of these tests and trials. Without proper design, implementation and oversight, such trials cannot be regarded as trustworthy. If the testing and trialling of live FRT continues to be so poorly designed, conducted and evaluated, these technologies may well become the Thalidomide of AI – embraced across the globe without rigorous trials of its efficacy or safety, even as it degrades the rights and foundations upon which liberal democratic societies rest.

[Longer abstract on Zenodo](#)

17:05 – 17:45 **Session 11**

Standard Track 1.B: Data-driven Transformations in Policy and Governance

Chair: Tom Smith

[37] *“The Education and Child Health Insights from Linked Data (ECHILD) Database: a new resource for evidence-based policy and practice”* Ruth **Gilbert***, Louise **Mc Grath-Lone**, Katie **Harron**, Erin **Walker**, David **Etoori** and Ruth **Blackburn**

[70] *“Recovering from the first Covid-19 lockdown: Economic impacts of the UK’s Eat Out to Help out scheme”* Gonzalo **Nunez-Chaim***, Nicolas **González-Pampillón** and Katharina **Ziegler**

[101] *“On the utilization of Disruptive Technologies for Municipality-wide Policy Making”* Maria **Tsourma***, Anna **Kougioumtzidou**, Anastasios **Drosou** and Dimitrios **Tzouvaras**

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† indicates Q&A participant at the live conference

17:45 – 17:55 Short Break

17:55 – 18:35 Session 12

Standard Track 2.D: Special Panel [73] - *Estimating and Forecasting Migration Flows*

Organiser: Peter **Smith**, University of Southampton

Chair: Jakub Bijak

[22] *“Monitoring the Numbers of European Migrants in the United Kingdom using Facebook Data”* Francesco **Rampazzo***, Jakub **Bijak**, Agnese **Vitali**, Ingmar **Weber** and Emilio **Zaghenni**

[24] *“Use of statistical modelling to predict international migration during 2020”* Nicola **Rogers** and Louisa **Blackwell***

[72] *“Extending the Integrated Modelling of European Migration”* Peter **Smith***, Georgios **Aristotelous** and Jakub **Bijak**

18:35 – 19:15 Session 13

Standard Track 3.B: *Policy Frameworks, Governance and Management of Data-driven Innovations*

Chair: Francesco Mureddu

[64] *“Towards evidence-based policymaking for robot governance: Harnessing robot experimentation to optimise the regulatory framing of emerging robot technologies”* Carlos **Calleja***, Hadassah G. **Drukarch** and Eduard **Fosch Villaronga**

[77] *“Data Responsibility & Corporate Social Responsibility”* Ziad **Al Achkar*** and Joanna **Van Der Merwe**

[87] *“Open innovation programmes related to data & AI: how do the entrepreneurial orientations of startups align with the objectives of public funders?”* Maria **Priestley*** and Elena **Simperl**

19:15 Day Close

Conference Programme (September 14th – 16th)

DAY 3, 16th September, London time

11:15 – 11:20 Day opening

11:20 – 12:00 Session 14

* indicates presenter at the live conference

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Standard Track 1.C: Special Panel [11] - *Informing policy for region and cities: data approaches for timely and granular evidence*

Organiser(s): Paolo **Veneri** (OECD), Ricardo **Barranco** (European Commission- EC) and Patrizia **Sulis** (European Commission – EC)

Chair: Justin Van Dijk

[11a] “*Understanding the geography of the health and economic impact of the COVID-19 pandemic*”, Paolo **Veneri*** (OECD)

[11b] “*Coastal tourism in the European Union: from COVID-19 shock to recovery*”, Ricardo **Barranco*** (European Commission- EC)

[11c] “*A multi-scalar analysis of ‘lonely places’ in the EU*”, Patrizia **Sulis*** (European Commission – EC)

12:00 – 12:40 **Session 15**

Special Track II.B: *Facilitating Data-Driven Innovation for Sustainability: Policy Frameworks and Measures for Data Governance*

Track Chair: Masaru **Yarime**

[84] “*Enabling Ethical Open Access Impact Analytics through Multi-stakeholder Data Governance Frameworks, Stewardship, Policy, and Community*” Christina **Drummond**, Jo **Lambert** and Dimitris **Pierrakos***

[112] “*Trust-Enhancing vs. Trust-Enabled Data-Driven Technology in Sustainable Smart City: The Case of COVID-19 Contact Tracing App in Hong Kong*” Wilson **Wong***

[91] “*The Sustainability Action Platform: a knowledge management mechanism for advancing global sustainability transitions?*” Ollie Bream-McIntosh, Amy **Burnett***, Ira **Feldman**, Jenna **Lamphere**, Thomas **Reuter** and Emmanuelle **Vital**

[105] “*Data sharing for value creation: An integrative literature review*” Johanna **Walker*** and Leslie **Carr**

12:40 – 12:50 **Short Break**

12:50 – 13:30 **Session 16**

Standard Track 2.E: Special Panel [36] - *Building health data infrastructure to manage epidemics in developing country contexts: Experiences from the Global South AI4COVID Program in Africa and Latin America*

Organisers: Laura **Acion**†, Enzo **Ferrante**, Sylvia **Kiwuwa Muyingo***, Amelia **Taylor** and Katie **Clancy***

Chair: Katie **Clancy**

* indicates presenter at the live conference

† indicates Q&A participant at the live conference

[36a] *“Introduction to the AI4COVID Program for Building Health Data Infrastructure in Developing Countries”* Katie **Clancy***

[29] *“ARgentinian Public Health research on data science and Artificial Intelligence for epidemic prevention (ARPH.AI)”* Laura **Acion†**, Enzo **Ferrante**, Verónica **Xhardez**, Victoria **Dumas**, Leonardo **Zanazzi**, Celeste **De Marco***, Fernando **Porta** and Cecilia **Sleiman**

[20] *“Building FAIR, sustainable, harmonised COVID-19 data to inform policy makers and researchers in Kenya and Malawi”* Sylvia **Kiwuwa Muyingo***, Amelia **Taylor**, Chifundo **Kanjala**, Jay **Greenfield**, Kobus **Herbst**, Henri **Tonnang** and Jim **Todd** And The Inspire Peach

[36b] *“Harnessing Artificial Intelligence and Big Data techniques to monitor, manage and forecast an epidemic: the case of COVID-19”* Jude Dzevela **Kong***, Bruce **Mellado**, Angela U. C. **Okpara**, Ali **Asgary**, George **Enow-Orock**, James **Orbinski**, Jianhong **Wu**, Miranda Teboh **Ewungkem**, Peter **Onwualu**, Pravesh **Debba** and Ngwa Gideon **Akumah**

13:30 – 14:10 **Keynote Lecture 2**

“A Blueprint for Social Data Foundation”

Dame Wendy **Hall**, Regius Professor of Computer Science, Associate Vice President (International Engagement), and Executive Director of the Web Science Institute, University of Southampton

Chair: John **Taysom**

Abstract: Our vision is to improve public health and patient care through responsible data access, collaboration and (re-)usage across academia, the public sector and industry by removing barriers and accelerating existing processes whilst maintaining the highest standards for data governance and security. At the centre of this aspiration lies the establishment of a Social Data Foundation (“the Data Foundation”) – an innovative trustworthy and scalable data-driven health and social care ecosystem overseen by independent data stewards – created to support multi-party data sharing whilst respecting societal values endorsed by the community.

14:10 – 14:40 **Networking Break**

14:40 – 15:20 **Session 17**

Standard Track 6.B: Data to Tackle Global Issues and Dynamic Societal Threats

Chair: Wilson **Wong**

[15] *“The unequal labor market impacts of COVID-19 in Developing Countries”* David **Newhouse**, Maurice **Kugler***, Mariana **Viollaz**, Isis **Gaddis**, Amparo **Palacios-Lopez**, Michael **Weber** and Daniel **Duque**

[61] *“A geospatial analysis of displacement in Afghanistan, using Nighttime Light data”* Anais **Dahmani** and Erwin **Knippenberg***

[68] *“Integration of GIS and big data for personalised COVID-19 advice in Hong Kong”* Veronica Qin Ting **Li*** and Masaru **Yarime**

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† indicates Q&A participant at the live conference

[21] *“Formal and Informal Approaches to Regulation of Artificial Intelligence in the Russian Federation”* Gleb **Papyshev***

15:20 – 16:00 **Session 18**

Standard Track 2.F: Data Technologies and Analytics for Policy and Governance

Chair: Barbara **Ubaldi**

[33] *“What makes administrative data “research-ready”? A thematic analysis of published literature”* Louise **Mc Grath-Lone***, Ruth **Blackburn** and Ruth **Gilbert**

[40] *“Rethinking regulation of emerging technologies in India: a co-regulatory approach”* Archana **Sivasubramanian** and Abhishek **Chakravarty***

[42] *“Revealing functional roles for built environment professionals using a network approach: An investigation of digital tasks and digital competencies”* Junqing **Tang***, Jennifer **Schooling**, Li **Wan** and Timea **Nochta**

[46] *“Using data linkage to assess the identification of vulnerabilities in administrative hospital data among a cohort of young mothers”* Francesca **Cavallaro***, Ruth **Gilbert**, Linda **Wijlaars** and Katie **Harron**

[38] *“A new indicator to improve measuring data access in Middle East and North Africa”* Uche Eseosa **Ekhatior-Mobayode***, Johannes **Hoogeveen**, Henri **Gannat** and Federica **Alfani**

16:00 – 16:10 **Short Break**

16:10 – 16:50 **Session 19**

Standard Track 5.B: Algorithmic Governance

Chair: Lauren **Maffeo**

[52] *“Open Algorithms: Lessons Learned from the Open Data Movement”* Natalia **Domagala**, Soizic **Penicaud*** and Simon **Chignard***

[62] *“Perspectives on Algorithmic Governance: Security in Domestic and Transnational Settings”* Kelly **Blount*** and Percy **Blount**

[94] *“Scaling collaborative policymaking: how to leverage on digital co-creation to engage citizens”* Andrea **Tocchetti**, Diletta **Di Marco***, Lorenzo **Corti** and Marco **Brambilla**

16:50 – 17:45 **Session 20**

Special Track I: Arguments, algorithms and tools: what do we need to shape policy and confront misinformation post-pandemic?

Track Chairs: Jaron **Porciello**, Stephan **Lewandowsky** and Ulrike **Hahn**

[54] *“Factual Corrections Eliminate the Effects of Misinformation About COVID-19 Vaccines”* Ethan **Porter***, Yamil **Velez** and Thomas **Wood**

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† indicates Q&A participant at the live conference

[83] *“Knowing what you know in the age of misinformation: Importance of metacognitive insight for beliefs and behavior regarding climate change and COVID-19”* Helen **Fischer***, Nadia **Said** and Markus **Huff**

[104] *“Assisting behavioral science and evidence-based policy making using online machine tools”* Stefan **Herzog***, Ulrike **Hahn**, Stephan **Lewandowsky** and Jaron **Porciello**

[119] *“How science reinforces liberal democracy through a more realistic picture of human nature”* Laura **Smillie*** and David **Mair**

17:45 **Closing Remarks - Zeynep Engin**, Founder of Data for Policy

17:50 **End of Conference**

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